

Deliverable 2.1

Best practice guide module field inspection

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1 Introduction and summary

1.1 Purpose of the document

The increased deployment of solar photovoltaic (PV) power plants globally has led to a growing need to address the challenges associated with the end-of-life (EOL) management of these systems. As PV capacity increases, it is crucial to establish sustainable practices for the characterization, decommissioning, and repurposing of PV modules to minimize environmental impact and maximize the recovery of valuable materials.

The scope of this document is to give recommendations for best practices when it comes to module health from the module being in the field to being sent to repair or recycling. This includes periodic inspection techniques, defect categorization, thresholds for replacements and handling of replaced modules.

1.2 List of definitions acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
PV	Photovoltaic
IR/IRT	IR/IRT Infrared/Infrared Thermography
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
EL	Electroluminescence
PL	Photoluminescence
IV	Current-Voltage
UVF	Ultraviolet Fluorescence
Voc	Open Circuit Voltage
Isc	Short Circuit Current
EOL	End-of-Life
STC	Standard test conditions (25 C, 1000 W/m ²)

2 Periodic in-field testing for module performance

This chapter outlines the most common in-field inspection techniques for assessing the health of PV modules. Note that we are focusing on in-field inspection techniques available in the PV plants rather than on testing in laboratory settings. The recommended inspection frequency is discussed within each technique's description, but it is important to note that these recommendations are only rough estimates. In practice, the frequency should be adjusted based on various factors, such as:

Description	Comments
Size of the plant	Smaller plants have higher costs per inspected megawatt (MW)
Age of the plant	Inspections are recommended shortly after startup to address production or installation defects. As the plant ages, the interval between inspections can be extended, provided the failure rate remains low
Failure rate	Plants with higher numbers of defects require more frequent characterization
Plant performance	Low performance may necessitate more frequent inspections
Available spare modules	When replacement modules are scarce, the incentive to identify defects is reduced
O&M contract	Inspection intervals may be specified within the operations and maintenance (O&M) contract
Warranty expiration	Consider inspecting modules before warranty expiration, particularly if there are concerns about potential warranty breaches
Electricity tariff and labour costs	The financial viability of inspections depends on the value of the electricity generated and labor costs

Additionally, certain events, such as lightning strikes, hail, or extreme wind, may necessitate specific in-field tests to assess any potential damage.

Testing during the installation phase is also recommended, often involving more comprehensive checks than those conducted during regular operations. However, these installation tests are beyond the scope of this report.

2.1 Visual Inspection

A full visual inspection of the plant can be time consuming and is not always cost-effective as a standalone task. However, visual inspection can be integrated with other activities and when moving around the plant on foot or by car. Some defects are easy to spot visually, such as modules with broken glass, as shown in Figure 1. Other defects such as burn marks, back sheet chalking, encapsulant discoloration, delamination, etc, can also be found by visual inspection. Chapter 8.1 includes a table of typical defects that can be identified visually.

FIGURE 1: EXAMPLE OF MODULE WITH BROKEN GLASS. IN THIS CASE IT LOOKS LIKE A HOT SPOT HAS BEEN THE CAUSE OF THE BROKEN GLASS. MODULES WITH BROKEN GLASS SHOULD BE REPLACED, BOTH FROM A PRODUCTION POINT OF VIEW, BUT ALSO BECAUSE THEY MAY CAUSE GROUND FAULTS ON THE INVERTER WHEN IT RAINS. PHOTO: JARRYD DUFFY, SCATEC

2.2 Thermal inspection

Modules that are not effectively converting sunlight into electricity or that have internal power dissipation will exhibit elevated temperatures. Infrared (IR) thermal imaging provides a heat map of a PV plant, identifying locations with abnormal temperatures, which typically indicate defects. While this method is excellent for pinpointing issues, it is less suited to provide detailed information about the underlying mechanism of the defect. IR thermography is the preferred method for large-scale PV plant inspections due to its speed and cost-effectiveness.

FIGURE 2: EXAMPLE OF INFRARED DRONE IMAGES FROM TWO DIFFERENT COMMERCIAL SUPPLIERS, THE PICTURE TO THE LEFT SHOWS AN ACTIVE BYPASS DIODE IN THE MIDDLE OF THE UPPER ROW AND THE PICTURE TO THE RIGHT SHOWS A HOTSPOT.

Thermal images can be captured in various ways, including handheld, car-mounted, or aerial methods (drones or airplanes). Drone-based inspection is most common, as it balances speed, cost, and data quality. To ensure that the inspection meets the necessary requirements the scan should be performed in accordance with IEC TS 62446-3:2017¹. The table in Chapter 8.2 outlines the best practices for conducting a detailed drone-based thermal inspection of a PV plant, covering key aspects from thermal and visual signature categorization to comprehensive documentation of the inspection parameters and findings. Most notably, the scan should be performed during normal, high irradiance, steady state operation with low soiling levels.

It is recommended to perform full plant IR scans multiple times during the lifetime of a PV plant. How often will depend on site specific factors as mentioned above, but a frequency of 1-4 years^{2,3,4} between scans is recommended, usually in the shorter range.

2.3 Emerging techniques

While visual inspection and IR thermography are widely used, other techniques are emerging that provide complementary or alternative insights. In common for most of these are that they are more time consuming and typically aim not for a full site inspection but rather for a representative sampling of the site.

2.3.1 Electroluminescence (EL) imaging

EL imaging has lately found its way out of the lab and several companies offer in-field inspection, either by drone or by a portable camera jig. EL images have a higher level of detail than IR images

¹ Photovoltaic (PV) systems-Requirements for testing, documentation, and maintenance-Part 3: Photovoltaic modules and plants (IEC TS 62446-3:2017)

² IEA PVPS O&M climates- Jahn et al., Guidelines for Operation and Maintenance of Photovoltaic Power Plants in Different Climates, IEA PVPS Report, 2022

³ SolarPowerEurope: Operation & Maintenance, Best Practice Guidelines, Version 5.0, 2021

⁴ IEC-TS-62446-3:2017, Photovoltaic (PV) systems – Requirements for testing, documentation and maintenance – Part 3: Photovoltaic modules and plants – Outdoor infrared thermography

and are particularly useful to identify defect mechanism that can help to determine the root cause of a defect. This may be useful for example in cases where warranty claims are involved. An example of an EL image is shown in Figure 3. While there is no specific standard or procedure for conducting EL inspections in the field, the table in Chapter 8.3 outlines the best practices for this process.

FIGURE 3: EXAMPLE OF EL IMAGE OF GOOD (LEFT) AND BAD (RIGHT) MODULE. THE MODULE TO THE RIGHT HAS A 25 % POWER THAN THE ONE TO THE LEFT, CAUSED MAINLY BY A REDUCED FILL FACTOR. THE SMALL SCATTERED DARK SPOTS ON BOTH MODULES ARE DUE TO THE DIFFERENT MULTI CRYSTALLINE SILICON GRAIN ORIENTATION.

This method is slower than IR thermography because it requires longer exposure times and powered modules. Since most inverters cannot provide external power, an external source is needed, and the strings must be disconnected and powered individually during inspection. Additionally, the lower intensity of the EL signal typically requires image collection to be done at night.

2.3.2 Photoluminescence (PL) and Ultraviolet Fluorescence (UVF) imaging

Photoluminescence (PL) and ultraviolet fluorescence (UVF) imaging technologies are becoming mainstream tools for PV module imaging in R&D projects with growing commercial interest⁵. A primary advantage of PL and UVF techniques is that they do not require electrical connections with modules, making them faster and less labour-intensive than EL imaging. Different approaches can be used here such as nighttime PL imaging systems using a portable light source and daylight PL where one avoids the need for a portable light source, but the luminescence signal is weaker⁶. Also new techniques apply optical modulation, or switching, of modules or entire strings of PV modules using control electronics. UVF also offers high-throughput imaging to detect cracks and defects. It can uniquely measure encapsulant degradation and differentiate old and new cracks at least 45 days after crack initiation⁷.

2.4 IV-curve tracing and other electrical measurements

After identifying a defective module, further electrical testing may be needed. Basic tests include measuring the open circuit voltage (Voc) and short circuit current (Isc) using a standard multimeter. While these tests can quickly confirm certain defects, others, like moisture ingress leading to increased series resistance, may require more detailed analysis through IV-curve tracing.

IV curve tracing is a key diagnostic tool for evaluating PV module performance, providing a complete picture of the module's current-voltage (IV) characteristics. In addition to the Voc and Isc, this also gives the fill factor of the module and hence the actual power rating. To perform these tests, conditions need to be stable, and irradiation should be high. IV curve measurements can also be done at the string level and some new inverters also has this functionality built in. On string level also impedance spectroscopy may be used to diagnose a string and to identify position of faulty modules.

In-field power measurements tend to have higher uncertainty than lab tests, often with deviations of at least 5%, depending on both operator and conditions. Chapter 8.5 contains additional information on conducting IV-curve tracing effectively.

3 Defect and Threshold Identification Criteria

When a defect is identified, operators must decide on the appropriate course of action for the module. If a defect is minor, it may be best to leave the module in place. However, for serious defects, a choice must be made regarding whether the module can be reused, repaired, or sent

⁵ O. Kunz, J.W. Weber, G. Rey, M. Juhl, and T. Trupke, "Daylight Photoluminescence Imaging via Optical String Switching," *Solar RRL*, Vol. 8, Iss. 19, Sep. 2024.

⁶ M. Vukovic et al, A review of imaging methods for detection of photoluminescence in field-installed photovoltaic modules, *Prog. Energy* 6 (2024) 032001, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2516-1083/ad4250>

⁷ W.B. Hobbs, S. Johnston, B. Gilleland, "Ultraviolet Fluorescence Bleaching Rates for New Cell Cracks," 2020 47th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC), Calgary, AB, Canada, 2020, pp. 2350-2355, doi: 10.1109/PVSC45281.2020.9300580.

for recycling. This chapter outlines recommended defect types and threshold criteria to guide these decisions.

For all in-field testing methods outlined in Chapter 2, the primary function is to detect defects; they do not directly quantify the impact on power production. Some defects may require follow-up testing to assess actual power loss, but these additional tests come at a cost. Often, it is more cost efficient to send modules with significant defects to a centralised module sorting or recycling facility without further on-site testing.

There are two primary considerations for module replacement: **performance** and **safety**. For performance-related issues, the decision is largely economic, factoring in the availability of replacement modules and the potential impact on plant efficiency. Modules in older plants are often obsolete, making replacement difficult without also replacing entire strings or even inverters to ensure electrical and mechanical compatibility. The recommendations in this chapter assume that spare modules are readily available.

- **Critical Defects:** These defects significantly impact the module's safety, performance, or reliability and require immediate attention. Examples include:
 - Cracks or breaks in the module glass or backsheet compromising structural integrity
 - Failed bypass diodes causing hot spots or power loss
 - Severe corrosion or moisture ingress posing an electrical safety risk
- **Non-Critical Defects:** These have minimal impact on safety or performance in the short-to-medium term but require monitoring over time as they can worsen. Examples include:
 - Minor blemishes or discoloration
 - Hotspots with slightly elevated temperatures
 - Loose cable connections or minor back sheet chalking

Regular inspections, as described in Chapter 2, are essential to monitor non-critical defects that could escalate to critical issues.

3.1 Thermal defect categories and thresholds

Most IR scan providers offer automated defect analysis, classifying defects into different categories and assigning a severity rating to the defect, such as low, medium and high severity. The classifications are based on the combined impact on production and safety. For example, a disconnected string will have a high impact on production, but only a slight temperature elevation and a low safety hazard. On the other hand, a high temperature hotspot, may be a safety hazard, but have limited impact on production.

High-severity defects typically require module replacement, while low-severity issues may be ignored unless their frequency indicates a larger health concern across the plant. Medium-severity defects may sometimes be left as is but should be monitored regularly. A plant with many medium and low severity defects that are left un-replaced should be scanned more frequent than a plants where few defects are detected.

The table in Chapter 8.4 shows examples of typical IR faults and suggested severity rating. For example, defects with temperatures exceeding 20°C above the module average generally classify as high severity, although exact thresholds can vary. Other defect classes, such as disconnected strings or activated bypass diodes, may also be considered high severity even with lower temperature differentials.

3.2 Visible defect categories and thresholds

For visual defects there are no recommendation from a supplier, so here the plant operator needs to have their own system for how to action the different types of visual defects. Some visual defects might require further testing, such as IV-curve tracing to determine necessary action. Chapter 8.1 includes guidelines for handling common visual defects encountered during inspections.

3.3 Emerging technologies

As discussed in Chapter 2.3, techniques like EL, PL, and UVF imaging provide detailed insights but are less established in terms of in-field defect classification and severity ratings. Service providers often apply their own systems for automated analysis and classification, which can serve as guidelines for using scan results effectively. EL and PL imaging, in particular, can provide detailed information on cell cracks. Chapter 8.6 offer guidance on how cell cracks at the cell and module level affect PV module performance.

4 Replacement process

The replacement process varies based on whether individual defective modules are being replaced or if replacements are part of a larger repowering or revamping initiative requiring bulk replacement.

4.1 Single module replacements

Following a PV plant inspection, such as visual or thermal assessments, modules with critical defects should be replaced. If on-site repair is not feasible, the module should be sent to a module sorting or recycling facility for further testing to assess whether it can be reused, repaired, or should be fully recycled.

4.2 Bulk replacements

In cases of bulk replacements, such as those driven by repowering or revamping campaigns, the process becomes more complex. While the specifics of a full repowering process are outside the scope of this report, it typically involves replacing modules from entire strings or inverters, often including many still-functional modules. In these instances, it is essential for the PV plant owner to determine how these modules should be managed and classified. Some classification options are outlined in the table below, and a visual inspection of the modules is recommended throughout the process.

Method	Pros	Cons
In-field IV scan	- Equipment is often available and allows for sorting by actual power output during replacement	- Time-consuming, weather-dependent, with power estimate uncertainty
IV-flasher on site	- Provides a more accurate power rating and higher throughput than traditional IV curve testing	- Costly to bring equipment on-site and requires more handling than standard IV testing
Thermal IR (drone or handheld)	- Faster than IV curve testing, with drone scans possible in advance	- Does not provide exact power rating, and requires module identification on the field
Sample testing	- Saves time by checking a few modules as representatives	- Limited insights since only a small sample is analyzed

5 Classification system for module Reuse, Repair, Recycle

This chapter discusses the classification and management of PV modules that have been removed from a plant. These modules can be directed into one of three primary pathways: reuse, repair, or recycling. The initial step for PV plant owners is to decide whether modules will remain on-site for future use or be transported to an external facility for sorting, repair, or recycling. Table 1 gives an overview of the typical workstreams for different defect types.

Retaining modules on-site provides the advantage of having compatible replacements readily available, while sending them to a specialized facility allows for more thorough testing and potential repairs at a reduced inspection cost, but with additional shipping costs. Whichever option is chosen, it is crucial to categorize, label, and store modules properly according to their classification.

TABLE 1: THE TABLE BELOW GIVES AN OVERVIEW OF TYPICAL DEFECTS THAT CLASSIFY FOR THE DIFFERENT WORK STREAMS. FOR BULK REPLACEMENTS THERE WILL USUALLY ALSO BE A LARGE QUANTITY OF MODULES WITHOUT DEFECTS THAT ARE SUITABLE FOR REUSE.

Defect	Recycling	Reuse	Repair
Broken glass	✓	-	-
Backsheet scratches	-	✓	✓
Moisture/corrosion in the module	✓	-	-
Broken interconnection strip(s)	✓	-	✓
>10% of cells broken	✓	-	-

Defect	Recycling	Reuse	Repair
Delamination at edges	✓	-	-
Burn marks on cells or ribbons	✓	-	-
Air bubbles at module edge, on/between cells	✓	-	-
Frame warped/broken	✓	-	✓
Junction box damaged	-	✓	✓
Cable damaged or loose	-	✓	✓
Cable connector(s) damaged	-	✓	✓

Classification pathways

1. Reuse:

Modules intended for reuse, often removed during bulk replacement, should be sorted based on their measured power rating if available. Categorizing modules into several power bins can help reduce mismatch losses when reassembling new strings. Using too many bins, however, can complicate sorting and storage

2. Recycling:

Modules classified for recycling will not return to the field or require extensive repairs beyond what is possible on-site. These modules should be sorted based on physical integrity (e.g., intact vs. broken frames or glass) to ensure proper handling and packaging. Modules sent to a recycling facility may undergo more detailed testing to determine if any are suitable for reuse or repair. The specific classification systems used by recycling facilities are outside the scope of this document.

3. Repair:

Some defects can be repaired directly on-site. For instance, junction boxes on certain modules may be easily replaced, even without removing the module from the field, reducing handling time. Following repairs, a module's electrical performance should be verified to confirm successful restoration. Table 2 lists defects that can typically be repaired on-site.

TABLE 2: THE TABLE LISTS DEFECTS THAT MAY BE POSSIBLE TO REPAIR ON SITE.

Defect	Repair solution
Failed bypass diode(s) in junction box, typically short-circuited	Replace bypass diode(s) by comparable ones. In the future this solution will often not be possible anymore, due to the current trend to fill more and more junction boxes with potting material

Failed bypass diode(s) with potting in the junction box	Remove the junction box and replace by new one (including diodes) that does not require potting
Junction box with internal or external damage	Remove junction box and replace by comparable new one
Damaged cables	Replace cables (including connectors)
Damaged or missing cable connector(s)	Mount new connector(s) on cables
Cracked backsheet over entire surface	Clean back-sheet and apply a coating on top of the original back sheet. This may have a high potential going forward because there are a lot of modules in operation today with a certain type of backsheet that are expected to fail in the future.
Backsheet chalking	Coating the backsheet with a silicone coating can help prevent or slow down further degradation because it blocks most of the UV and water, which play a role in the chalking mechanism.

6 Packaging Handling and Storage

Proper packaging, handling, and storage of PV modules are essential to preserve their condition, whether they are designated for reuse, repair, or recycling. This chapter outlines best practices to ensure that modules are safely stored and transported.

6.1 Storage guidelines

Modules require temporary storage whether they are intended as on-site spares or will be shipped to external facilities. Ideally, modules should be stored in a dry, well-ventilated area, protected from direct sunlight and moisture. Inside warehouses are preferred; however, if unavailable, modules can be stored in containers or other covered storage. If only external storage is available, it should be limited to no more than three months in an uncontrolled environment. Extra precautions, such as covering connectors to prevent exposure to moisture or sunlight, are recommended. Framed modules should not be stacked glass-glass and with the reverse side up as this may cause water to accumulate when it rains rain.

For external storage, select a well-prepared, level, and drained area, free from vegetation. Modules should be placed close together and covered with a weatherproof tarp for short-term storage to protect against rain and sunlight.

Modules at the end of their life may also be stored externally but should be covered similarly to maintain the pallet's structural integrity.

Strapping must be done on both long side and short side (picture to be updated)

FIGURE 4: EXAMPLE OF EXTERNAL STORAGE IN UNCONTROLLED ENVIRONMENT. THE MODULES SHOULD IDEALLY BE COVERED BY A WEATHER-PROOF TARP TO PROTECT AGAINST RAIN AND SUNLIGHT.

6.2 Packaging for transport

Once modules are classified, they can be packaged for transport to the appropriate facility. Place modules horizontally on suitable pallets, adhering to the original equipment manufacturer's (OEM) recommendation for long-term storage and transportation. Once the correct quantity is in position, suitable strapping should be applied to the pallet-model combination on both the short and long edge. Finally, suitable wrapping should be placed around the full pallet to provide extra support to the modules.

FIGURE 5: REFERENCE IMAGE OF STACKING OF MODULES FOR TRANSPORT (COURTESY OF ROSI: END-OF-LIFE PV PANELS PALLETS STACKING GUIDE)

FIGURE 6: VERTICALLY STACKED MODULES AS RECEIVED FROM MANUFACTURER. NOTE ALSO THE CORNER CARDBOARD PROTECTORS.

For modules being transported long distance off site, it is recommended to stack vertically along the modules long edge. Once the pallet is full, the vertically stacked modules are to be strapped together as per above. Note that cardboard corner protectors are to be applied to every second module to avoid potential damage to the frame and glass of the modules. Finally, suitable wrapping should be placed around the full pallet to provide extra support to the modules.

Modules that have reached end of life can be packaged less conservatively. Here it is recommended to stack modules horizontally on a suitable pallet. Stacking height should not exceed 40 modules. Once the pallet is full, suitable strapping should be applied to the pallet-model combination on both the short and long edge. Additional wrapping can be applied, if available, to provide additional support to the pallet of modules.

6.3 Lifting and transportation procedures

Once a sufficient quantity of modules is available, transportation to their next destination can be arranged. It is important here that pallets are not double stacked and that loading and offloading are considered.

Best practice is to commence loading on site closest to the truck. Two pallets should be loaded alongside one another (long edge) down the centre of the trailer. Additional pallets are to then be added down the length of the trailer. This provides even loading and weight distribution to ensure safe transportation to the final destination.

FIGURE 7: EXAMPLE OF TYPICAL TRANSPORT DO'S AND DON'TS

7 Environmental Considerations

Environmental considerations are crucial when managing the storage, transportation, and recycling of PV modules. This chapter provides guidelines to ensure environmentally responsible practices that adhere to waste management regulations and promote sustainability in PV module end-of-life handling.

Adhering to waste management regulations

It is crucial to ensure that the storage, transportation, and recycling of damaged PV modules adhere to all relevant waste management regulations. Currently, the European Union is the only region that has categorized PV modules as electronic waste, but the legislation may not be well-suited for the unique characteristics of PV technology. It is important to develop more targeted waste regulations for PV modules, both within the EU and in other countries, to enable a sustainable second-hand market and facilitate proper recycling.

Promoting recycling initiatives

Encouraging and supporting recycling initiatives for damaged PV modules is essential to minimize the environmental impact of module replacements. This includes establishing clear recycling pathways, providing financial incentives for recycling, and ensuring the availability of certified

recyclers that can handle PV module materials responsibly. Developing comprehensive recycling guidelines and traceability systems can help optimize the recycling process and maximize material recovery.

Minimizing the environmental impact of module replacements

The storage and handling of damaged PV modules should be done in a way that minimizes the potential for environmental contamination. This includes preventing the release of hazardous materials, such as lead or cadmium, and ensuring the proper disposal of any non-recyclable components. Implementing best practices for module storage, transportation, and decommissioning can help mitigate the environmental impact of module replacements and end-of-life management.

Recommendations for environmentally responsible practices

To support environmentally responsible practices, consider the following recommendations:

- Develop international standards for the quality inspection and reuse of PV modules, with the involvement of relevant stakeholders and standardization bodies.
- Advocate for the creation of waste legislation that is specifically tailored to PV modules, accounting for their unique characteristics and enabling a sustainable second-hand market.
- Establish clear guidelines for the safe storage, handling, and transportation of damaged PV modules to prevent environmental contamination.
- Encourage the development of comprehensive recycling programs and infrastructure, with a focus on maximizing material recovery and responsible disposal of non-recyclable components.
- Provide educational resources and training to personnel involved in the management of damaged PV modules, ensuring they understand the environmental implications and best practices.
- Collaborate with regulatory authorities, industry associations, and environmental organizations to align practices with the latest developments in waste management and environmental protection.

8 APPENDICES

The appendices provide additional resources, checklists, tables, and detailed guidelines to support the best practices outlined in this document. These resources are designed to assist PV plant operators, technicians, and maintenance personnel in effectively implementing inspection, replacement, and recycling processes.

8.1 Visual inspection defect types

Glass plate broken	Backsheet scratches	Moisture/corrosion in module	Broken interconnection strip(s)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
>10% of cells broken	Delamination at edges	Burn mark on cells or ribbons	Air bubbles at module edge, on/between cells
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Frame warped/broken	Junction box damaged	Cable damaged or loose	Cable connector(s) damaged
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

FIGURE 8: EXAMPLE OF CHECKLIST FOR VISUAL INSPECTION

TABLE 3: DEFECTS THAT CAN BE IDENTIFIED BY VISUAL INSPECTION

Defect type	Appearance and Origin	Impact	Detection	Mitigation
Front/backsheet delamination 	<p>Local separation of the layers between the front glass and the encapsulant or between the encapsulant and the cells. Visible as bubbles or brighter areas.</p> <p>Rear: Separation/bubble formation on the back sheet. Can originate from production failures or develop in the field.</p>	<p>Delamination may initially have little impact on production but can lead to moisture ingress, corrosion, optical losses, and current mismatch if it reaches electrical connections. Severe delamination risks electrical hazards. Prompt attention is needed, especially in hot, humid conditions.</p>	<p>Visual inspection, insulation testing</p>	<p>Replace modules with direct safety risk and modules that fail insulation testing</p>

<p>Cell cracks</p>	<p>Can be caused during production, installation, and operation (heavy forces such as wind, hail, snow, etc). Small cell cracks (micro-cracks) become visible when they form snail tracks or when photobleaching or delamination takes place along the cracks. A snail track is a discoloration of the silver paste of the front metallisation of solar cells which occurs typically 3 months to 1 year after installation of the PV modules.</p>	<p>Often low impact on module efficiency but might accelerate other degradation mechanisms. Risk for hotspots and burn marks due to inactive cell parts. For in-depth information about cell cracks and impact see Chapter 8.6</p>	<p>Visual inspection, EL, UV, (also high resolution IRT, indirectly with IV)</p>	<p>Corrective: Replace modules with direct safety risk.</p> <p>Preventive: Adequate transport, mounting and maintenance procedures to avoid excessive force on the modules.</p>
<p>Encapsulant or back sheet discoloration</p>	<p>The degradation of the encapsulation or back sheet materials is becoming visible as a light yellow to dark brown discoloration.</p> <p>This is most often associated with the degradation of EVA encapsulant in older modules, but this problem was reduced by improved stabilization of the polymer for newer modules.</p>	<p>Can cause higher degradation rates. Low safety impact for EVA discoloration but might be a concern for backsheet discoloration if it causes loss of mechanical properties.</p>	<p>Visual inspection (IV, IRT)</p>	<p>Check module certification, ensure ground fault detection.</p> <p>Corrective: Replace modules with direct safety risk</p>
<p>Backsheet cracking</p>	<p>Any damage of the backsheet (surface or whole stack) that is visible as crack, burst or scratch.</p>	<p>Can cause moisture ingress and corrosion, electrical insulation failure and potentially ground faults.</p> <p>Detection: Visual inspection (Insulation testing)</p>	<p>Visual inspection (Insulation testing)</p>	<p>Preventive: Ground fault detection, check certification.</p> <p>Corrective: Replace modules with direct safety risk</p> <p>If module is repairable, consider backsheet repair, for instance silicone repair coating</p>

<p>Backsheet chalking</p>	<p>White powder is detectable on the external surface of the back sheet. It can be seen by passing a finger over the backsheet. Caused by degradation of backsheet material.</p>	<p>Low impact on production but might be a sign of future cracks or initial backsheet failure</p>	<p>Visual inspection (Insulation testing)</p>	<p>Preventive: Regular inspections to monitor progress and development of more severe faults.</p> <p>Corrective: application of silicone coating.</p>
<p>Burn Marks</p>	<p>Visible with the naked eye as burnt, blackened areas.</p> <p>Caused by parts of the module becoming very hot because of one of many underlying issues (electrical connections, severe hotspots, etc),</p>	<p>Severe cases can cause a fire if there happens to be flammable material around.</p> <p>An infrared image can identify whether the area is continuing to be hot and/or whether the current flow has stopped in that part of the circuit.</p>	<p>Visual inspection, IRT</p>	<p>Corrective: Replace modules with direct safety risk</p>
<p>Broken Glass</p>	<p>Glass is cracked locally or over the full area of the module. Breaks can happen in production or during operation due to mechanical force or thermal gradients or stress A relatively commonly observed failure in the field is glass breakage of frameless PV modules caused by the clamps that fasten the module. Glass/glass modules have been seen to be more sensitive to glass breakage assumingly due to the use of thinner glass.</p>	<p>Module mechanical integrity is compromised when the glass is broken. Over time glass breakage leads to loss of performance due to cell and electrical circuit corrosion caused by the penetration of oxygen and water vapour into the PV module. Modules with broken glass is also known to cause inverter trips due to earth faults.</p>	<p>Visual inspection, IRT</p>	<p>Preventive: Adequate transport, installation and maintenance procedures.</p> <p>Corrective: Replace modules with direct safety risk. Broken glass modules should normally be replaced when possible.</p>

8.2 Requirements table for IR scan

TABLE 4: THE TABLE SHOWS SUGGESTED REQUIREMENTS FOR DRONE BASED IR-SCAN BASED ON DETAILS FROM IEC-TS-62446-3 ⁸

Step	Description
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⁸ IEC-TS-62446-3:2017, Photovoltaic (PV) systems – Requirements for testing, documentation and maintenance – Part 3: Photovoltaic modules and plants – Outdoor infrared thermography

Data Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capture high-resolution thermal (infrared) and visual (RGB) images of all the operative PV modules using a drone-mounted camera system. - Ensure the thermal camera's technical specifications (e.g., thermal sensitivity, accuracy) are suitable for the inspection requirements. - Data capture: When capturing thermal images, the pilot should understand how to calculate the appropriate ground sampling distance (GSD) and camera settings for desired image resolution of at least 3 +/- 0.5 cm/pixel. • Ideally the imaging should be done at a solar elevation where self-shading from adjacent arrays is not present. • Inspection path parallel with PV array, i.e., the horizontal image edge aligns with the long edge of the PV array. • Lateral speed must be low enough to avoid image blur in both infrared thermography (IRT) and visual images. • Wind speed below 8 m/s.
Inspection conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PV plant should be operating, free of partial shading, and modules should be clean, and free of dirt or surface liquids. -Ensure Weather Parameters: Ideal sunny and clear, recommended irradiance above 600 W/m² in the plane of the PV module with minimal cloud cover. Ideally with less than 60% humidity. -Ensure there are no grid curtailment.
Data Processing & Software Selection	<p>Use software that complies with the requirements specified in IEC TS 62446-3:2017, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to process and analyse radiometric thermal images - Functionality to accurately geolocate and index the thermal images to the PV plant layout (Digital Twin) - Tools for anomaly identification, classification, and reporting - Compliance with data security and integrity standards
Thermal / Visible Signature Categorization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accurately identify and document the various thermal and visual anomalies observed during the inspection - Use defined categories to classify the detected issues, such as Hot Spots, Hot Bypass Diodes, Delamination, Browning/Discoloration, Cell Mismatch, Junction Box Defects - String Mismatch - Proper categorization enables accurate representation of the inspection results and facilitates appropriate and timely issue resolution
Plant Indexing and String Name Convention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Index all images according to the plant's as-built documentation - Document the methodology used for estimating the module position and the associated error - Ensure accurate association between the inspection data and the plant's physical layout

Documentation of Thermal Image Acquisition Parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide details on the methodology for determining the normal module operating temperature reference used in the calculation of defect temperature difference (ΔT) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Document the positioning equipment used (e.g., UAS) and its specifications - Describe the general flight pattern - Specify the IR camera's technical details (NETD, absolute temperature accuracy, emissivity, reflected temperature, etc.) - Document the RGB camera specifications - Include the IR camera's calibration certificate - Explain the methodology for determining module position and the positioning error estimate - Confirm compliance with relevant industry standards (e.g., IEC TS 62446-3:2017) - Identify the directory containing the labelled raw radiometric IR image files - Record the cloud coverage and type at the time of image capture
Summary of Findings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The software should provide a digital twin of the PV plant that summarizes the metadata and information for each module affected by thermal anomalies

8.3 EL requirements

TABLE 5: PROCESS FOR ELECTROLUMINESCENCE (EL) IMAGING FOR DEFECT DETECTION BASED ON STANDARD IEC/TS 60904-13

Field-based EL	Key Points
Equipment and techniques for electroluminescence imaging.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Portable EL equipment and cameras - Drone-based EL inspections - Mobile test stations brought to the installation site
Recommended Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a test plan outlining the scope and objectives - Clean the modules to ensure accurate imaging results - Determine the specific modules/areas to be inspected and the optimal timing (e.g., one hour after sunset) - Capture EL images in a dark environment to minimize external light interference
Sample size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IEC technical specification IEC/TS 60904-13 recommends sampling 10-20% of the total number of modules in a plant. This sample size can be adjusted based on factors such as the plant's age, historical performance, and any known issues.

Documentation and Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Record all visible defects, such as cracks, hotspots, and delamination -Annotate the EL images to highlight and explain each issue
Standards and Specifications	- The IEC technical specification (IEC/TS 60904-13) provides guidelines for EL inspections in the field

8.4 IR image interpretation

TABLE 6: THIS TABLE SHOWS EXAMPLES OF COMMONLY ENCOUNTERED IR ANOMALIES:

Thermal anomaly representation	Fault type	Temperature signature	Definition	Possible Cause	Remarks
Visual degradation 	Single cell	Temperature difference from few degrees and upwards. Temperatures above 20 ° C are considered high severity.	Assess by thermal pattern and visual image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slow degradation - bird droppings - delamination 	Stress factors: temperature, UV
Heat Pattern 	Single cell	Temperature difference from few degrees and upwards. Temperatures above 20 ° C are considered high severity.	Uneven heat pattern or overheating specific points	Internal problems such as cell crack, micro cracks or snail tracks	Stress factors: thermal cycling, mechanical load. cells overheated due to failures in the cell and module manufacturing process
Cell rupture 	Single cell	Temperature difference from few degrees and upwards. Temperatures above 20 ° C are considered high severity.	Significant overheating of a part of a cell. Similar characteristics, between cell cracks and broken ribbons mechanisms	- Cell breakage	Stress factors: thermal cycling, mechanical load. Increase of series resistance Rs. Stress factors: thermal cycling, mechanical load.
Patchwork pattern 	Short-circuited module	1 to 3 cell substrings at temperatures (10-35°C) above module average temperature. Temperatures above 20 ° C are considered high severity.	Individual cells are randomly distributed and significantly heated; pattern is indicative of a short, circuited module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Failure/short circuit in bypass diode(s). - Lightning can cause this - Wrong connection of the module 	Diodes could potentially be replaced.

<p>Substring open-circuited</p>	<p>Substring disconnected</p>	<p>One or two cell substring(s) at a uniform temperature (3-5 °C) above the average module temperature. Considered medium to high severity due to power loss.</p>	<p>Assess by thermal pattern and visual inspection on junction box</p>	<p>- Disconnected cell ribbon (in junction box typically)</p>	<p>Stress factors: electrical (Ribbon could be fixed)</p>
<p>Open-circuited module</p>	<p>Module out</p>	<p>The Δt is low-moderate and uniform for all the module surface, (3-5 °C) above the average of adjacent modules. Considered high severity.</p>	<p>Assess by thermal pattern and visual inspection in wiring or junction box</p>	<p>- The module is open-circuited, the cause could be bad open-circuited wiring between modules or in disconnected cell ribbons (junction box)</p>	<p>The ribbon could be fixed</p>
<p>Shunted cells Shadowing</p>	<p>Single cell</p>	<p>Temperature difference typically 5-15°C</p>	<p>Assess by thermal pattern and visual image. Shadowing not necessarily permanent</p>	<p>Shaded cell due to, vegetation, bird droppings, lightning rods or neighbor module row</p>	<p>Stress factors: thermal cycling, mechanical load.</p>
<p>Potential Induced Degradation</p>	<p>PID</p>	<p>-Δt more severe at low irradiance than STC - Δt higher for medium degraded cells than for severely degraded ones.</p>	<p>Assess by thermal pattern, IV curve test and EL Imaging</p>	<p>The effect is linked to the negative potential of each PV module.</p>	<p>Stress factors: temperature, relative humidity, electromechanical Recoverable by applying reverse voltage</p>
<p>Broken ribbon(s)</p>	<p>Single-cell</p>	<p>Strong or severe Δt in a part or a whole cell, depending on the number of broken interconnecting ribbons Drastic Power loss</p>	<p>Assess by thermal pattern, if all (usually two) interconnecting ribbons fail at the same cell the submodule goes off.</p>	<p>Faulty or displaced soldering</p>	<p>If submodule goes off current flows through a bypass diode Stress factors: thermal cycling, mechanical load.</p>
<p>Open String</p>	<p>String OC</p>	<p>The whole string at a uniform temperature (3-5 °C) above the average of adjacent strings.</p>	<p>Assess by thermal pattern and string fuse condition.</p>	<p>Blown string fuse, cable fault, disconnected</p>	<p>Replace string fuse.</p>

		Considered high severity			
<p>Heated Junction Box</p>	Junction Box	The temperature of the Junction Box is higher than adjacent areas. Temperatures above 20°C are considered high severity			Replace junction box if possible
<p>String Short Circuit</p>	String SC	The thermal image may show a concentrated, bright spots or a distinct hot area within the string, indicating the location of the short circuit. Considered high severity	Assess by thermal pattern and wiring condition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - String wired in reverse at the combiner - Module-to-module connection errors. 	It is important to identify and address such anomalies promptly, as prolonged exposure to higher temperatures can lead to decreased panel efficiency, potential damage, or even safety hazards.

8.5 Module and string level IV-curve testing

Level	Key Steps
Module-level IV Curve Tracing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clean the PV modules to remove any dirt, debris, or shading materials - Calibrate the measurement equipment and confirm the reliability - Align the module with the sun to maximize solar irradiance. - Disconnect the module from the string before testing - Aim for a representative irradiance level, typically around 1000 W/m² - Use a reference cell to measure stable irradiance during the tests - Document the test parameters, IV curve data, and any observations
Data and Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use a standardized format or software to organize and store the data for easy retrieval and analysis - Include any observations or abnormalities during the testing process - Document the test parameters, such as module details, date, and test conditions using a checklist - Record the obtained IV curve data accurately, including voltage and current values, and repeat the measurements if there is too much variance in irradiation on-site

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Record both the measured and STC corrected power measurements - Compile the results of IV curve tracing in a report, outlining the performance data collected, any identified issues, and recommended actions for optimization or repair
Equipment	<p>PV analyzers with Measurement of the I-V Curve of a module or a string up to 1500V/10A - 1000V/15A (note that newer modules may have higher cu (e, g: HT, Entec Solar, FlukeShpul include Anaysis software,</p> <p>Able to connect an irradiance sensor and temperature probe and collect data at the time of the IV Tracing.</p> <p>Calibration!!</p>
String-level IV Curve Tracing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow the same preparation steps as module-level testing - Disconnect the String combiner Box from the PV array. - Open the fuse or circuit breaker to isolate the string from the rest of the system. - Aim for a representative irradiance level, typically around 1000 W/m² - Use a reference cell to measure stable irradiance during the tests - Document the test parameters, IV curve data, and any observations
Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -PV analyzers with Measurement of the I-V Curve of a module or a string. Make sure the analyzer is valid for the voltage and current that is to be measured. Typical voltages are 1000-1500 V for string measurements and 40-50 V for modules. Currents are usually in the range of 10-20 A. -If several strings are going to be tested, aim for equipment with Autosequence that Check - String by String without disconnecting any cable. -Able to connect an irradiance sensor and temperature probe and collect data at the time of the IV Tracing. -Confirm that equipment has a valid calibration certificate that has not expired

8.6 Cell Cracks based criteria/considerations for module reuse, repair and recycle

The understanding of cell cracks in silicon solar cells is well-developed, with various techniques available for detection and analysis. The choice between recycling and reuse depends on the extent of the damage, the potential for material recovery, and the economic and environmental considerations. Before we start going deeper into these considerations, let's review a bit of a background on cell cracking.

Cell cracks in silicon solar panels can occur via various phenomenon. They can occur during manufacturing of solar panels due to damage caused by processes such as laser scribing and soldering. They can also occur during transportation, installation and maintenance of the solar

panels. Environmental factors like, a single exposure to a very low temp. (-30C), wind loading, thermal cycling and hail impact are also well known to cause cracks in silicon solar panels.

The effects of cell cracks on the performance (reduced efficiency and power loss) of silicon solar cells depends on several factors such as number of busbars, cell orientation, number of bypass diodes, orientation of cell cracks, cumulative crack length, and many more. Disposition criteria based on these factors is summarized in the table below. These disposition criteria can be very useful when it's time to decide on whether to reuse repair or recycle a given solar panel.

Parameter LEVEL	Parameter	Criteria/Considerations	Supporting Data	Comments	Additional Data	Reference/Link
Cell Level	# of Busbars	≥ 5 busbars limits potential loss of cell current to 10% or less	<p>Fig. 3: Calculation of the worst-case scenario for cell area or current loss if an open crack occurs just outside one of the outermost wires as a function of the number of wires.</p>	Larger the # of wires/busbars, smaller the area that can be completely lost at the edges of the cells, and lower the resistive power losses when open cracks form between busbars.		https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283302929_Solar_panel_design_factors_to_reduce_the_impact_of_cracked_cells_and_the_tendency_for_crack_propagation
	Metallization Paste/Pattern	Limited literature on crack effects due to metallization paste/pattern		Improvements to the Ag and Al paste compositions, and to the geometries of the busbars, fingers, and rear Al/Ag overlap regions have potential to reduce the severity of crack formation and crack-related metallization contact loss and power loss.		https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283302929_Solar_panel_design_factors_to_reduce_the_impact_of_cracked_cells_and_the_tendency_for_crack_propagation
Cell Level	Cell Size/Orientation	Half-cell, long orientation has lower risk of cell fracture		At a loading level of 2800 Pa, 20 of the full-cell and 40 of the half-cell short orientation module's cells surpassed 98 % fracture probability. In comparison, the maximum probability of cell fracture in the half-cell long orientation module is only 39 % for the center most 4 cells.		https://doi.org/10.1109/JPHOTOV.2022.3192118
Module Level	Type of Backsheet	Glass (G//G) modules rarely have cell cracks	If back glass is broken/cracked, module should be scrapped, regardless of the cell conditions	Very hard to find cracked cells for modules with intact back glass; in other words, back glass will break before you see any cell cracks		https://youtu.be/Zti4gLvixXM?si=4t1c94Rs_V7PE9Qz

Parameter LEVEL	Parameter	Criteria/Considerations	Supporting Data	Comments	Additional Data	Reference/Link																												
Module Level	String Wiring Configuration	Parallel is preferred		Shading of the cell roughly simulates the condition of having open cracks that cause the same percentage of lost area. Parallel configuration performs better under shading.		https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283302929_Solar_panel_design_factors_to_reduce_the_impact_of_cracked_cells_and_the_tendency_for_crack_propagation																												
Module Level	Module Stiffness	Preferred characteristics: 1. Thick front glass 2. Glass backsheet 3. Encapsulants with high modulus values 4. Sturdy frames and/or frames with additional stiffening elements such as crossbars.		Increasing the stiffness of modules will reduce the amount of deflection for a given front-side load, thus reducing the tensile stress levels and cracking within the modules.																														
Module Level	# of Bypass Diodes	Modules with 3 bypass diodes vs. 1-2 can reduce power loss in modules with cell cracks		Higher the number of bypass diodes, lesser the amount of power loss resulting from cracked cells (ref. 18)																														
Cell Level	Crack Orientation	Diagonal cell cracks in 2 or fewer cells to avoid significant effects on power 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="4">DIAGONAL CRACK PERFORMANCE INDICATORS</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Number of Affected Solar Cells</th> <th>Approximate Area Broken (mm²)</th> <th>T-test Value</th> <th>Significant/Not Significant Effect on the P₀ Power Performance</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1 mm² - 83 mm²</td> <td>0.40 - 0.66</td> <td>Not Significant, Since t < 2.56</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>83.83 mm² - 169.7 mm²</td> <td>1.22 - 1.86</td> <td>Not Significant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>172.7 mm² - 256.6 mm²</td> <td>2.51 - 2.71</td> <td>Significant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>257.5 mm² - 344.4 mm²</td> <td>2.65 - 2.70</td> <td>Significant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>345.1 mm² - 424.3 mm²</td> <td>3.12 - 3.35</td> <td>Significant</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	DIAGONAL CRACK PERFORMANCE INDICATORS				Number of Affected Solar Cells	Approximate Area Broken (mm ²)	T-test Value	Significant/Not Significant Effect on the P ₀ Power Performance	1	1 mm ² - 83 mm ²	0.40 - 0.66	Not Significant, Since t < 2.56	2	83.83 mm ² - 169.7 mm ²	1.22 - 1.86	Not Significant	3	172.7 mm ² - 256.6 mm ²	2.51 - 2.71	Significant	4	257.5 mm ² - 344.4 mm ²	2.65 - 2.70	Significant	5	345.1 mm ² - 424.3 mm ²	3.12 - 3.35	Significant			https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7980824
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Parameter LEVEL	Parameter	Criteria/Considerations	Supporting Data	Comments	Additional Data	Reference/Link
Cell Level	Crack Orientation	Perpendicular/Multiple direction cell crack effects have not been addressed in literature 	N/A	No information is available in literature		
Cell Level	% Isolated Area due to Cracks	% Module isolated area due to cracks (referred to as "Crack Size" in Dhimish & Kettle 2021 and "Crack Percentage" in Dhimish & Hu 2022 and measured using EL images of modules with and without cracks) $\leq 1.5\%$ resulted in degradation rates below 1% and $\leq 11\%$ resulted in output power loss below 10%		<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9661056</p> <p>https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-022-16546-z</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1109/JPHOTOV.2022.3228104</p>		

Parameter LEVEL	Parameter	Criteria/Considerations	Supporting Data	Comments	Additional Data	Reference/Link
Module Level	# of Cracks	Modules with ≥ 10 cracks were observed to have annual Pmax degradation rates above 1.5%.		Data is based on 925 modules evaluated in "All-India Survey of Photovoltaic Module Reliability" across 37 sites, age range of 1-25 years, and 6 technology types. More cracks were observed in young modules vs. older modules, rooftop vs. ground-mount, and small/medium vs. large installations.		https://research.mnre.gov.in/api/publications/All_India_Survey_of_Photovoltaic_Module_Reliability_2016_Executive_Summary.pdf
Module Level	Brightness of Isolated Areas Caused by Cracks	Brightness of isolated areas has high correlation with power loss	<p>Cumulative crack length (L), the proportion of area isolated by cracks (PA), brightness (normalized mean grayscale value G) of the whole cell image (G1), and brightness (normalized mean grayscale value G) of isolated areas caused by cracks (G2)</p>	<p>- Modules in EPRI study underwent 4 different accelerated aging test sequences, followed by outdoor exposure; analysis determined that brightness of isolated areas caused by cracks (G2) had the highest correlation with Pmp decrease.</p> <p>- Modules that experienced mechanical loading had more severe cracks and worsening severity of isolated areas.</p> <p>- G2 is an especially strong descriptor for Voc with a correlation coefficient of 0.94. Darker isolated areas have lower Voc.</p>		https://doi.org/10.1109/JPHOTOV.2022.3228104
Module Level	Cumulative Crack Length	Cumulative crack length has high correlation with power loss	<p>Cumulative crack length (L), the proportion of area isolated by cracks (PA), brightness (normalized mean grayscale value G) of the whole cell image (G1), and brightness (normalized mean grayscale value G) of isolated areas caused by cracks (G2)</p>	<p>- Modules in EPRI study underwent 4 different accelerated aging test sequences, followed by outdoor exposure; analysis determined that cumulative crack length has high correlation with Pmp decrease.</p> <p>- Modules that experienced mechanical loading had more severe cracks and worsening severity of isolated areas.</p>		https://doi.org/10.1109/JPHOTOV.2022.3228104

